

Experimental Analysis of Sub-GHz RF Communication for in-Water Wearables in Swimming Applications

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Abstract—This paper investigates the experimental evaluation of sub-GHz radio frequency (RF) communication systems for wearable devices used in swimming applications. Specifically, we analyze the feasibility and performance of two frequency bands, 169 MHz and 434 MHz, in supporting near real-time data transmission from in-water sensors to above-water receivers. A series of controlled experiments were conducted in an Olympic-size swimming pool, with the transmitter placed at various depths and distances. We measured key communication metrics, including Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) and packet loss, across three different antenna placement scenarios: on the water surface, under the water surface, and submerged at 10 cm depth. Both frequencies were tested using evaluation boards with comparable antenna setups and power configurations. The results show that the 169 MHz band consistently provides stronger signal performance and better range, while the 434 MHz band offers acceptable performance under specific configurations with lower power consumption. Our findings highlight the potential of sub-GHz RF technologies for enabling reliable in-water communication in wearable swimmer monitoring systems for real-time aquatic telemetry for sports and health applications.

Index Terms—In-water communication, swimming tracking, swimming sensors, RF communication

I. INTRODUCTION

Wearable technology has become a cornerstone in modern sports performance monitoring, enabling the collection of physiological and motion data during training and competition. In aquatic sports such as swimming, however, real-time data transmission remains a largely unsolved problem due to the physical limitations of wireless communication in water [1]. Conventional technologies like Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) and Wi-Fi operate at 2.4 GHz and are known to suffer from severe signal attenuation and distortion when submerged, rendering them impractical for continuous in-water data transmission.

The ability to reliably transmit physiological or motion data from swimmers in near real-time could unlock significant advances in personalized coaching, rehabilitation, and remote health monitoring [2]. To this end, sub-GHz radio frequency (RF) communication—specifically in the 169 MHz and 434 MHz bands—has emerged as a promising alternative. These

lower frequencies offer better penetration through water and the water–air interface, potentially enabling communication between submerged wearable sensors and receivers located above the surface.

In this work, we present the experimental evaluation of a sub-GHz RF communication system for in-water wearable applications. We perform a series of controlled tests in a full-size swimming pool, assessing system performance under various operating conditions. This study aims to inform the development of reliable, low-power, real-time communication systems for aquatic wearables, bridging the gap between swimmer data acquisition and real-time telemetry.

This work is part of the EU-TRAINS project [3] that aims to design and build a made-in-Europe ecosystem for multisport training, healthy lifestyle, and remote patient monitoring based on cloud-edge continuum of AI-featured body sensors. In the specific case of swimming, the primary objective is to develop a non-invasive, water-resistant wearable device capable of continuously tracking key physiological parameters, such as heart rate and respiration, during water-based sports and training sessions.

This paper primarily concentrates on the near real-time communication aspect of the project, outlining the design of a system capable of maintaining a stable communication link through the challenging water-air interface.

One of the most commonly adopted solutions in similar contexts is based on BLE due to its low power consumption and ease of integration. However, conventional BLE-based systems face substantial limitations in aquatic environments. Specifically, while they can collect and store physiological data during an activity, they are typically unable to transmit this data in real time to a receiver located outside the water. Instead, these systems often log the data locally and upload it only once the user has exited the water. This post-activity transmission undermines the goal of near real-time monitoring, which is a central requirement of the present effort.

Given these challenges, the system architecture can be divided into three key subsystems:

- The in-water sensing unit, responsible for acquiring physiological data from the user in real time;
- The in-water communication unit, which transmits data within the aquatic environment;
- The in-air communication unit, which receives the transmitted data once it crosses the water surface and relays it to external systems or monitoring devices.

In this paper, we focus on understanding the feasibility of Sub-GHz RF communication for real-time communication of a swimmer towards a receiver located outside of the water. The final goal is to enable a real-time analysis of the swimming technique and biometric values by a coach without waiting for a post-processing analysis.

II. RELATED WORK

In the literature, we can find some existing work that treats the problem of in-water communication. The authors in [4] present a comprehensive study on underwater radio wave propagation in freshwater using a high-gain axial mode helical antenna operating at 433 MHz. They design and encapsulate the antenna to prevent direct water contact, optimizing performance by filling the capsule with distilled water. Their simulation results align well with theoretical predictions, confirming the antenna’s effectiveness in freshwater. Finally, they support their findings with measurements conducted in a swimming pool, highlighting the impact of surface reflections on signal attenuation.

Similar to the findings in [5], research on packet-based communication in freshwater at 2.4 GHz indicates that high data rates can only be sustained over very short ranges. Electromagnetic simulations at the same frequency, as explored in [6], show an attenuation of 40 dB at a distance of 0.5 meters. Additionally, measurements reported in [7] at 420 MHz demonstrate that the received signal power drops to nearly 0 μ W over a 0.5-meter transmission path.

The authors in [8] propose a reliable wireless communication protocol for coach-based augmented biofeedback in swimming, using wearable inertial sensors to send real-time data to coaches. Acknowledging the challenges of radio transmission underwater, they develop a Wi-Fi-based system with a block-selective repeat protocol that handles intermittent channel availability. They validate the approach with tests on professional swimmers, showing the protocol ensures accurate and efficient data delivery. This system supports real-time performance monitoring and feedback, enhancing motor learning and training quality.

The authors in [2] propose a wireless communication system for real-time motion monitoring in swimming training, using ESP32 microcontrollers and MPU6050 accelerometers. The devices are arranged in a master–slave configuration, where each sensor-equipped slave device transmits movement data to a master device via the ESP-NOW protocol. This communication method allows low-latency, reliable data exchange over short distances without relying on an internet connection. A local web server on the master device manages user interactions and displays results. The system uses gesture comparison

Fig. 1. Transmitter (right) and Receiver (left) at the swimming pool

algorithms to analyze swimming motions and provide real-time feedback, demonstrating the effectiveness of peer-to-peer communication for coach-assisted swim training.

While prior work has demonstrated the feasibility of short-range underwater RF communication and the potential of wearable systems for swim monitoring, many of these solutions remain limited by range, power constraints, or real-time capabilities. Moreover, few studies have systematically evaluated the performance of sub-GHz RF communication in full-size swimming pools under realistic conditions. To address these gaps, in this work, we present an experimental evaluation of a sub-GHz RF communication system for in-water wearable applications. This study aims to inform the development of reliable, low-power, real-time communication systems for swimmer wearables, bridging the gap between swimmer data acquisition and real-time telemetry.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We evaluated and compared the performance of two distinct sub-GHz frequency bands, 169 MHz and 434 MHz, both of which are widely utilized in various wireless communication applications. These frequency bands are integral to enabling long-range communication in low-power wireless systems such as Internet of Things (IoT) networks, sensor networks, and other similar devices that require efficient and reliable data transmission over extended distances.

A. Communication technology

To carry out these tests, two evaluation boards provided by Silicon Labs were selected (Fig. 1).

The 169 MHz device is capable of transmitting at a maximum power output of 19 dBm, which is well-suited for long-range communication. The transmission power of 19 dBm is particularly beneficial for applications that require robust communication in outdoor environments or over large areas. For the 169 MHz device, the receive sensitivity was recorded

at -112 dBm, which indicates a high level of sensitivity to low-power signals. The evaluation board (EVB) used in the test is powered by a 1500 mAh rechargeable battery, which provides sufficient power for extended testing sessions without the need for frequent recharging. To enhance signal transmission and reception, the device uses a 169 MHz whip antenna, which is known for providing good range and signal clarity in wireless communication systems. All of the electronic components, including the evaluation board and the associated hardware, are housed within a robust Hammond 1555J2F42GY enclosure. This enclosure measures approximately 160x90x60 mm, providing sufficient protection for the components while ensuring that the system remains portable and easy to handle during the testing process.

In contrast, the device operating at 434 MHz demonstrated a lower maximum transmission power of 14 dBm. While this value is somewhat lower than that of the 169 MHz device, it still strikes a favourable balance between transmission range and energy efficiency. The reduced transmission power can be beneficial in applications where power conservation is critical. The receive sensitivity for the 434 MHz device was measured at -109 dBm, which, while slightly less sensitive than the 169 MHz device, still reflects good performance in receiving weak signals over long distances. The trade-off between transmission power and receive sensitivity at different frequencies plays a critical role in determining the suitability of each frequency band for specific use cases. Similar to the 169 MHz device, the EVB operating at 434 MHz was placed inside the same robust enclosure used for the 169 MHz system. The same 1500 mAh rechargeable battery was used to power the 434 MHz device, maintaining uniformity in power supply conditions between the two tests. However, the 434 MHz device utilized a different antenna specifically designed for optimal performance at this frequency.

RF module specifications are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I
RF MODULE SPECIFICATIONS

Frequency	Modulation	Tx Power	Sensitivity	Data Rate
169 MHz	GFSK	19 dBm	-112.2 dBm	38.4 kbps
434 MHz	OOK	14 dBm	-109.9 dBm	4.8 kbps

B. Test configurations

The experimental tests were conducted in an Olympic-sized swimming pool located near Pisa, chosen for its ideal characteristics to carry out wireless communication tests in a controlled and well-defined environment. During the experiments, the following technical setup was used for data collection: a receiver device was positioned at the poolside in a way that allowed it to be clearly visible and capable of intercepting the data packets sent by the transmitter device. The receiver, in turn, transmits the received packets via serial communication, along with the corresponding RSSI (Received Signal Strength Indicator) value for each packet received, in order to assess the signal strength and propagation behaviour under various distances and depth conditions.

Fig. 2. Scenario 1: antenna completely out of the water

The transmitter device, responsible for sending data packets in burst mode, was configured to transmit 1000 packets of fixed length (16 bytes each), with a transmission interval of 100 milliseconds (100 ms) between each packet. This setup allowed for the collection of high-density packet measurements, useful for analyzing signal quality and packet loss in various propagation scenarios.

The transmitter device was positioned at different distances and depths within the pool to simulate various transmission conditions. The experimental setup was divided into three main configurations, each differing in the position and orientation of the transmitter’s antenna relative to the water level.

1) *Scenario 1*: In this first setup (see Fig. 2), the transmitter device was positioned on the water surface, with the antenna completely out of the water. This configuration allowed observation of the signal behaviour under aerial-surface transmission conditions, without direct interference from the water, but with a possible effect due to signal reflection or diffraction on the water surface itself.

2) *Scenario 2*: In the second setup (see Fig. 3), the transmitter device was positioned with the antenna completely submerged beneath the water surface. This configuration allowed exploration of the effect of partial antenna submersion, where the signal propagates through the air-water interface, creating a transition between the two environments and studying the potential changes in signal behaviour at this intermediate depth.

3) *Scenario 3*: In the third setup (see Fig. 4), the transmitter device was positioned with the antenna 10 cm below the water level. This condition represented a more complex transmission scenario, where the water acts as a propagation channel, with potential attenuation, reflection, or distortion effects due to the dielectric properties of water, which could alter the communication quality compared to air. This configuration was chosen to closely simulate the conditions that a swimmer might experience during training, where the device is worn and operated while the swimmer is moving through the water. The antenna placement at this depth replicates the typical submersion depth that a swimmer’s wearable equipment would encounter when partially submerged, such as when swimming in shallow or moderate-depth pools. By closely mimicking this real-world scenario, the setup allows for more accurate testing of the communication system’s performance under conditions that resemble the movement and orientation changes a swimmer might undergo.

Fig. 3. Scenario 2: antenna completely submerged

Fig. 4. Scenario 3: antenna 10 cm below the water level

IV. RESULTS

In this section, we report the results obtained in the three configurations previously described at various distances. The purpose of these tests is to assess how well the devices perform under realistic conditions. The graphs that follow in this section illustrate the behaviour of the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) during the burst cycle. In particular, the blue line in the graphs represents the RSSI of the signal operating at 169 MHz, while the orange line corresponds to the signal at 434 MHz. These graphs provide a clear visual comparison of how each frequency behaves in terms of signal strength over time.

Furthermore, the number of lost packets is also considered. This is a critical metric for evaluating the reliability and overall performance of the wireless communication. A higher number of lost packets indicates potential issues such as poor signal reception, interference, or environmental factors that hinder the transmission.

A. Results: Scenario 1

In the scenario, with the antenna just above the water (see Fig. 2), the performance does not present particular problems as expected due to the limited water impact factor. In the surface transmission scenario, both modules achieved near-perfect reliability up to 37.5 m. At 12.5 m, the 169 MHz module showed a stronger RSSI (-38 dBm) compared to 434 MHz (-65 dBm), with 0% packet loss for both.

At 50 m (see Fig. 5), RSSI degraded to -78 dBm (169 MHz) and -91 dBm (434 MHz), with packet loss increasing to 13.5% and 9.4%, respectively.

These results show that while the 169 MHz device provides better performance at short and mid distances, its advantage diminishes beyond 37.5 m. The occurrence of packet loss is particularly important in real-world communication systems, as it can significantly affect the reliability and quality of the transmitted data. For applications requiring near real-time communication, such as in aquatic or remote sensing systems, even small amounts of packet loss can result in data gaps or incomplete information, which may compromise the system's overall performance. These results indicate that, as the distance

Fig. 5. Scenario 1 @ 50 m RSSI trends

increases and the devices are pushed to their limits, both devices face challenges related to signal degradation and packet loss. The increase in packet loss at longer distances emphasizes the need for robust error correction mechanisms, adaptive modulation schemes, or other methods to improve the system's reliability under these conditions. Further investigation into the impact of different environmental factors, transmission power, and antenna configurations will be crucial to understanding how to minimize packet loss and optimize system performance for long-range communication.

B. Results: Scenario 2

In Scenario 2 (see Fig. 3), the transmitter device was carefully positioned so that the antenna was placed just below the water's surface, allowing it to be partially submerged. This setup was designed to explore the effects of antenna submersion, where the signal could interact with both the air and water, passing through the air-water interface.

In the experiment conducted at a distance of 12.5 meters, the RSSI at 169 MHz showed a consistent trend with an average value of -76 dBm, indicating stable performance throughout the test. The device operating at 169 MHz demonstrated reliable signal strength, reflecting its stable transmission characteristics in the test environment. On the other hand, at 434 MHz, the results exhibited a less uniform pattern. Such irregularities are important to note, as they highlight the sensitivity of the 434 MHz device to changes in positioning and orientation. While the device operating at 169 MHz displayed more stable performance under these conditions, the 434 MHz device exhibited performance variations, likely due to its weaker transmission power and susceptibility to minor shifts in positioning. As such, careful attention to these variables is necessary for achieving optimal performance, particularly in real-world swimming applications where dynamic conditions and movement may be prevalent.

In this test setup, slight packet loss was observed: approximately 0.3% at 169 MHz and 2.8% at 434 MHz. In real-world applications, minor packet loss could affect performance. To reduce this, error correction or adaptive techniques could be implemented to enhance communication reliability.

At a distance of 25 meters, the packet loss percentage observed in the experiment increased significantly compared

to the 12.5-meter test. At 169 MHz, packet loss surged to 63%, while at 434 MHz, it reached 52%. This was a notable increase in packet loss, indicating that the communication quality deteriorated as the distance between the transmitter and receiver grew. Interestingly, despite the higher packet loss at 169 MHz, the RSSI trend at this frequency was stronger, with an average value of -86 dBm, compared to -99 dBm at 434 MHz. This discrepancy suggests that while the signal strength at 169 MHz was stronger, other factors contributed to higher packet loss at this frequency. These factors could include increased interference, multi-path propagation, or other environmental conditions that affect signal transmission, beyond just the RSSI levels. On the other hand, while the 434 MHz signal was weaker, it might have been less affected by such issues, leading to lower packet loss. This highlights the complexity of wireless communication, where signal strength alone doesn't always correlate with the actual packet loss observed, and multiple variables must be considered for accurate performance evaluation.

At a distance of 37.5 meters (Fig. 6), similar RSSI values were recorded as those observed at shorter distances, but the packet loss percentage exceeded 95%. This dramatic increase in packet loss highlights a critical issue in maintaining reliable communication over longer distances when the device is underwater, even when the received signal strength remains relatively strong. The fact that the RSSI values were still fairly high at -90 dBm for both frequencies suggests that the signal was still detectable, but the degradation in packet delivery implies that other factors, such as interference, noise, or multipath propagation, were significantly impacting the transmission quality. It is a clear indication that signal strength alone is not always a reliable indicator of communication success. At greater distances, the signal becomes more susceptible to environmental disruptions, including water absorption, obstacles, and changes in the physical environment that contribute to signal scattering and loss. This highlights the inherent challenges of wireless communication, especially in aquatic environments, where maintaining data integrity over long ranges requires overcoming substantial limitations beyond just signal attenuation. These results emphasize the need for further improvements in communication protocols and error correction mechanisms to ensure more reliable performance over extended distances. Finally, at a distance of 50 meters, the communication link was completely lost, with nearly all of the transmitted packets being lost.

C. Results: Scenario 3

In the third test setup (Fig. 4), the transmitter device was strategically positioned with the antenna submerged 10 cm below the water's surface.

The results in Fig. 7 focus on the 12.5-meter distance, where the signal behaviour at both 169 MHz and 434 MHz demonstrated comparable trends. Despite the 8 dBm difference in RSSI between the two frequencies, both frequencies exhibited similar patterns of signal strength over the test distance. However, even at this relatively short distance of 12.5 meters,

Fig. 6. Scenario 2 @ 37.5 m RSSI trends

Fig. 7. Scenario 3 @ 12.5 m RSSI trends

a noticeable packet loss was observed. Specifically, 22% of the packets transmitted at 169 MHz were lost, while 12% of the packets transmitted at 434 MHz failed to be received. While these loss percentages may initially seem relatively high, they are still considered to be within an acceptable range given the conditions of the test. Notably, the transmission antenna was positioned 10 cm below the water's surface during the test, a factor that can significantly affect signal propagation. The antenna's submersion depth, although small, still introduced attenuation due to water absorption and interference, which contributed to the observed packet loss. Despite this, the results indicate that the communication system is performing reasonably well under the given conditions, and the packet loss observed is not excessively high for real-world underwater scenarios, especially when considering the complexities of wireless communication in aquatic environments.

The graphs for the 25-meter, 37.5-meter, and 50-meter distances are not shown, as the packet loss at these distances reached a staggering 100%. This suggests that, at these extended ranges, the communication link was entirely lost, and no data packets were successfully transmitted. The complete failure of the communication system at these distances highlights the challenges of maintaining reliable wireless connectivity over long ranges, especially in environments where water attenuation plays a significant role. Despite the initial successful transmission at shorter distances, the signal quality deteriorated sharply, ultimately leading to a total breakdown of communication at 25 meters and beyond.

D. Summary and Discussion

The experimental results clearly show that in-water RF communication is significantly influenced by both the propagation channel and the transmission distance. In surface conditions, where the signal can travel through air, the communication range is robust, with signals successfully transmitted over distances of tens of meters. However, once submerged, especially in near-surface conditions or at varying depths, the effective communication range is greatly reduced.

Following extensive analysis of the experimental test results, the decision was made to prioritize the use of the 434 MHz frequency over 169 MHz for short-range in-water communication. This decision is supported by a range of technical advantages observed during practical in-water trials, particularly with respect to signal reliability, energy efficiency, and ease of system integration into wearable formats. One of the most significant findings during the testing phase was that the 434 MHz band exhibited substantially lower packet loss rates (Table II), especially in situations involving partial or intermittent submersion. Even in challenging aquatic conditions, the 434 MHz signal maintained greater communication stability. In contrast, the 169 MHz frequency was far more prone to interruptions and signal degradation, which led to increased data loss and unstable connections. This superior resilience of the 434 MHz signal makes it far more suitable for applications where communication reliability is essential, such as near real-time monitoring of swimmers in motion.

Beyond transmission performance, the 434 MHz system also demonstrated notable advantages in power consumption. Devices operating in this band require less energy to maintain a stable connection, which is a crucial factor in the design of wearable systems intended for prolonged use. Longer battery life directly translates into extended training sessions without the need for frequent recharging, enhancing the usability and practicality of the technology for athletes and coaches alike.

Another decisive factor in favour of the 434 MHz option is the smaller antenna size required for effective operation at this frequency. Antenna miniaturization is particularly important when developing compact, swimmer-friendly devices that must be both lightweight and hydrodynamically efficient. The reduced antenna footprint allows easier integration into sleek enclosures or even within the fabric of swimwear, without compromising comfort or movement. Considering all these factors, enhanced transmission reliability, improved energy efficiency, and superior integration potential, the 434 MHz frequency clearly emerges as the most appropriate choice for short-range in-water communication in wearable systems.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper outlines the hardware and test setups designed to evaluate water-based communication in the EU-TRAINS project. The primary goal of these tests is to analyse the performance of wireless transmissions at 169 MHz and 434 MHz under both submerged and surface conditions, providing insight into the feasibility of using these frequencies for in-water communication. This work aims to go in the direction

TABLE II
PACKET LOSS (%) AT VARIOUS DISTANCES

Scenario	Distance	169 MHz	434 MHz
Subsurface (2)	12.5 m	0.3%	2.8%
	25 m	63.4%	51.9%
	37.5 m	97.2%	95.0%
	50 m	99.7%	99.9%
10 cm Under (3)	12.5 m	22.7%	12.1%
	25 m	99.7%	99.8%
	37.5 m	100%	99.9%
	50 m	100%	100%

of a real-time swimming tracking, overcoming the challenges of in-water communication.

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